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Price Strategies And Consumer Brand Loyalty Of Water Bottling Company In Yenagoa Bayelsa State (A Case Study Of Fido Refreshing Water)

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of Price Strategies and Consumer Brand Loyalty of Bottling Water Industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, the study implores a survey research design and use Spearman rank correlation to investigate the relationship between cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing, customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty. The significance of the study on "Price Strategies and Consumer Brand Loyalty of a Water Bottling Company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State (A Case Study of Fido Refreshing Water)" extends to various stakeholders, including the government, policy makers, business owners, investors, employees, researchers, and academicians. The findings reveal strong evidence of significant positive relationships between the three pricing strategies cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing, and customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty for the water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Keywords: Price Strategies, Brand Loyalty, Bottling Company, Cost-based pricing, Competition-based pricing, and Customer perceived value-based pricing.

INTRODUCTION

The water bottling industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, plays a crucial role in meeting the increasing demand for clean and potable water. With the growing awareness of health and wellness, consumers are becoming more discerning about the brands they choose for their bottled water consumption. Fido Refreshing Water, as a prominent player in this industry, faces the challenge of not only providing high-quality water but also strategically managing its pricing to foster consumer brand loyalty.

Manufacturing can be described as the process of converting raw materials into finished products (Osuagwu, 2016), taking place through the use of manpower, machines and tools to achieve the desired output; that is, finished goods. Manufacturing entities are distinguished from other forms of business through innovation and the supply of commodities on a large scale. Manufacturers are clustered under the various categories of production, such as basic and fabricated metal products, clothing and footwear, pulp and paper products, food, beverages and tobacco, apparel, chemicals, rubber and plastics, and furniture (Abdullahi, et al., 2019).

Amesi (2011) however argued that strategy is all about competitive position, about differentiating yourself in the eyes of the customer as the case may be, about adding value through a mix of activities different from those used by competitors. Amesi also viewed strategy as a combination of the ends (goals) for which the firm or institution is striving and the policies by which it is seeking to get. Strategies are high level plans set out to achieve one or more goals under conditions of uncertainty. Strategies are important because the resources available to achieve these goals are usually limited. According to Amine and Cavusgil (2011) see strategy generally as involving setting goals,

determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions. A strategy describes how the ends (goals) will be achieved by the means (resources).

Pricing strategy is considered to be one of the more critical components of the marketing mix (Product, Place, Price and Promotion) and is focused on generating revenue and ultimately profit for the company. Pricing strategy is paramount to every organization involved in the production of consumer goods and services because it gives a cue about the company and its products, a company does not set a single price but rather a pricing structure that covers different items in its line (Aremu & Lawal, 2012). Price strategies are essential components of marketing that significantly influence consumer behavior. For water bottling companies, establishing optimal pricing structures is crucial for maintaining a competitive edge and attracting a loyal customer base. The pricing decisions made by Fido Refreshing Water can impact not only its market share but also the perceived value of its brand in the eyes of consumers.

Customers are the driving force for profitable growth and customer loyalty can lead to profitability (Asugman, et al., 2017). For a customer, loyalty is a positive attitude and behavior related to the level of re-purchasing commitment to a brand in the future (Barczak et al., 2007). Loyal customers are less likely to switch to a competitor solely because of price and they even make more purchases than non-loyal customers (Barney, 2006). Loyal customers are also considered to be the most important assets of a company and it is thus essential for vendors to keep loyal customers who will contribute long-term profit to the business organizations (Borden & Neil, 2004). Attempt to make existing customers increase their purchases is one way to strengthen the financial growth of a company (Bowers & Closs, 2016). Furthermore, organization's financial growth is dependent on a company's ability to retain existing customers at a faster rate than it acquires new ones. Managers should understand that the road to growth runs through customers-not only attracting new customers, but also holding on existing customers, motivating them to spend more and getting them to recommend products and services to the other people.

Consumer brand loyalty is a valuable asset for any business, contributing to long-term success and profitability. This study therefore covers the relative effect of prices strategy using the predicting variable such as cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing and customer perceived value-based pricing on brand loyalty. In the case of Fido Refreshing Water, understanding how their pricing decisions influence consumer loyalty is imperative for strategic business planning.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

In current business activities, the success or failure of any business organization hinge on how best such organization can fulfill its customers and this act places huge task and responsibility by way of marketing on any organization intending to excel at satisfying their customers and clients. The duty involves identifying the precise needs of their customers/clients and deciding on how best to handle their products and services so as to satisfy the wants of both prospective buyers and sellers bottle water companies are increasing in Nigeria, yet the level of failure in their services indicate that ineffective relationship with customer seems to be pronounced.

While the literature is replete with studies examining the interplay between pricing strategies and consumer brand loyalty in various industries, a noticeable void exists regarding the water bottling sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced exploration of how Fido Refreshing Water's pricing strategies influence consumer loyalty within the unique regional context. By doing so, this research seeks to contribute valuable insights that can inform the strategic decision-making processes of both Fido Refreshing Water and similar enterprises in the region.

In the following sections, we will delve into the theoretical underpinnings of pricing strategies, explore the dynamics of consumer brand loyalty, and analyze the specific context in which Fido Refreshing Water operates.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study seeks to examine the effect of price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state with special focus to Fido Refreshing Water. Other specific objectives are:

1. To examine the relationship between cost-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

2. To examine the relationship between competition-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.
3. To examine the relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

1.4 Research Questions

The above objectives gave rise to the listed research question:

1. What is the relationship between cost-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state?
2. What is the relationship between competition-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state?
3. What is the relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study (stated in their null form):

HO₁: There is no significant Relationship between cost-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

HO₂: There is no significant Relationship between competition-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

HO₃: There is no significant Relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

METHODOLOGY

Research design helps the researcher develop a mental image of the structure for gathering the data and the analysis that will follow as observed by Asika (2006). The techniques use on analyzing the streamline of this survey design since the research was mainly interested in finding out things as they exist in their natural setting (Obasi, 2001). It is the framework for study used as a guide in collecting and analyzing data. This research will make use of the survey research design while carrying out the study. Survey design refers to eliciting data from targeted population through either questionable or interview instrument and conclusions.

The population of the study is a census of all items or subjects that possess the characteristics or that have knowledge of the phenomenon being studied (Asika, 2006). The population for this study comprises all employees of Fido of water bottling company in Yenagoa metropolis.

The data that will be generated for the purpose of this study shall be analyzed with the aid of the spearman rank order correlation coefficient statistical tool. This statistical tool became imperative due to the fact that the scale used in this study are ordinal scale and the topic of this study deals with relationship between two variables. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23 shall be employed for the analysis of the variables involved. The spearman ranked order correlation statistical tool is symbolically given as Rho whose formula is given as

$$\text{Rho} = 1 - \frac{6\sum d^2}{n(n^2-1)}$$

Rho lies between -1 and +1

A sample is a part of a population. It is a sub group of observation from a large population in order to make inferences about the characteristics of the large population. Since it would neither be possible nor practicable to study employees of Fido of water bottling company in Yenagoa metropolis, which is a total of 28 staff. Therefore, this study will make use of the total population of 28 employees

The data for this study will be collected using a self-administered questionnaire (primary data). Questionnaires are appropriate for gathering the views of a large number of people about a particular phenomenon (Stroh, 2000). This instrument that will be adopted for this research is the questionnaire which will be validated and reliable.

The questionnaire is divided in two sections. Section A seeks to elicit responses on personal data of the respondents while Section B examines the price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company. The study will make use of three dimensions which are cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing and customer perceived value-based pricing.

The instrument used for this study will be validated by the researcher's supervisor and two specialists in Faculty of Management Science where to ascertain if the instrument will measure what it ought to

measure. Inputs from these resource persons will be taken into consideration and necessary changes will be affected.

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach Alpha Method will be adopted to estimate the internal consistency coefficient of clusters A, B, C and D of the questionnaires will be A, 1-3 respectively with an overall coefficient of B, 4-6, C, 6-9 and D, 10-12. Cronbach Alpha statistics will be used because the instruments are in clusters and items are not dichotomously scored. Cronbach Alpha is also considered appropriate as it ensured the homogeneity of the items on the clusters. Based on the Cronbach Alpha the variables are cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing and customer perceived value-based pricing.

All the variables of this study are measured in ordinal scale. This study will examine the relationship between price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company. Both the dimensions of independent variables and the measures of the dependent variables are measured with structured questionnaire along the five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagreed to strongly agreed.

RESULTS

The first section covered the presentations of data on: The relationship between the price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. The presentation and analysis took the form of tabulation and explanation of the data collected from the completed questionnaires. The following analyses were based on the data obtained from the response to questionnaires.

Data Presentation

Table 1 Questionnaire Administration and Retrieval

Variables	Responses	Percentage
Returnable	25	90.6%
Non-Returnable	3	9.4%
Total	28	100%

Source: field work; 2024

A total of 28 copies of questionnaire were issued, and 25 questionnaires were retrieved representing 90.6% of the sample which is satisfactory. So, this analysis is based on 25 responses.

Table 2 Sample Characteristics

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender (sex)	Male	17	68
	Female	8	32
	Total	25	100%
Marital Status	Single	14	56
	Married	11	44
	Total	25	100%
Business Experience	1-3 years	13	52
	4-5 years	8	32
	7-9 years	2	8
	10 years and above	2	8
	Total	25	100%

From the table above the percentage of male and female that responded to this research questionnaire were 17 and 8 which represent 68% and 32% respectively, which indicates higher percentage of male response to female. With respect to marital status 14 representing 56% of the respondents are single while 11 representing 44% of the respondent are married. Finally, the Table above shows the Business experience of respondent and their percentage most of the respondents have worked in the organization for about 1-3 years.

Descriptive Analysis

The respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agree with the following statements on Price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state by using a scale of 1 – 5 where SA: Strongly Agree = 5, A: Agree = 4, N: Neutral =3, D: Disagree =2, SD: Strongly Disagree =1. Their responses are presented in table 4.2 below. Also, the mean score was used to test the degree of significance of each statement relating to price strategy.

Table 3 Descriptive Analysis on Cost-Base Pricing

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
The pricing of this bottled water reflects its quality.	3.0748	0.88433	25
The price of this bottled water is fair compared to other brands.	3.2517	1.19842	25
The company’s pricing strategy influences my purchasing decisions.	3.6463	1.02572	25
Discounts and promotions influence my decision to purchase this bottled water.	3.4082	1.19218	25
Total mean and standard deviation	3.3453	1.07516	25

Source: Authors Computation Using SPSS version 23 *Highly considered (mean ≥ 2.50)

Table above shows that majority of the respondents agreed with all the statements measuring cost-based pricing. The overall mean of 3.35 shows that the level of cost-based pricing is moderate.

Table 4 Descriptive Analysis on Competition-Based Pricing

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
The price of this bottled water is competitive compared to other brands.	4.0204	0.60216	25
I trust the quality and safety of this brand’s bottled water.	4.0340	1.15518	25
I trust the quality of this bottled water despite its competitive pricing.	2.9456	0.90495	25
The pricing of this bottled water is appropriate given the market competition.	3.5918	1.03206	25
Total mean and standard deviation	3.6480	0.92359	25

Source: Authors Computation Using SPSS version 23 *Highly considered (mean ≥ 2.50)

Table above shows that majority of the respondents agreed with all the statements measuring competition-based pricing. The overall mean of 3.65 shows that the level of competition-based pricing is moderate.

Table 5 Descriptive Analysis on Customer Perceived Value-Based Pricing

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I believe that this bottled water offers more value than competing brands.	3.0952	0.92406	25
The pricing of this bottled water meets my expectations for its quality.	3.6259	0.98767	25
I consider the price of this bottled water a good investment for my health.	4.0748	0.69330	25
I believe the quality of this bottled water is higher than other brands at similar prices.	4.1088	0.77750	25
Total mean and standard deviation	3.7262	0.84563	25

Source: Authors Computation Using SPSS version 23 *Highly considered (mean ≥ 2.50)

Table above shows that majority of the respondents agreed with all the statements measuring customer perceived value-based pricing. The overall mean of 3.73 shows that the level of customer perceived value-based pricing is moderate.

Table 6 Descriptive Analysis on Customer Brand Loyalty

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
The brand's reputation influences my loyalty.	3.4626	0.99500	25
I trust the quality and safety of this brand's bottled water.	3.4490	0.86153	25
This brand of bottled water consistently meets my expectations.	4.1156	0.60270	25
I remain loyal to this brand even if other brands are cheaper.	3.6122	0.92491	25
Total mean and standard deviation	3.6599	0.84604	25

Source: Authors Computation Using SPSS version 23 *Highly considered (mean ≥ 2.50)

Table above shows that majority of the respondents agreed with all the statements measuring customer brand loyalty. The overall mean of 3.66 shows that the level of customer brand loyalty is moderate.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the three hypotheses stated in the first chapter of this research were tested using Spearman Rank Correlation of Coefficient through the use of SPSS software to determine the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable in this study, that is, to determine the predictive power of Price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

HO₁: There is no significant Relationship between cost-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

			COST-BASED PRICING	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY
Spearman's rho	COST-BASED PRICING	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.975**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	25	25
	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY	Correlation Coefficient	.975**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above indicates a positive correlation coefficient of 0.975 between Cost-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. This means that an increase in Cost-Based Pricing will lead to an increase in customer brand loyalty. The p-value of 0.000 suggests that Cost-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state at 5% level of significance. This suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. We therefore concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between Cost-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

HO₂: There is no significant Relationship between competition-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

			COMPETITION-BASED PRICING	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY
Spearman's rho	COMPETITION-BASED PRICING	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.972**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	25	25
	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY	Correlation Coefficient	.972**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above indicates a positive correlation coefficient of 972 between Competitor-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. This means that an increase in Competitor-Based Pricing will lead to an increase in customer brand loyalty. The p-value of 0.000 suggests that Competitor-Based Pricing has a significant relationship with customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state at 5% level of significance. This suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. We therefore concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between Competitor-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

HO₃: There is no significant Relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

			CUSTOMER PERCIEVED VALUE-BASED PRICING	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY
Spearman's rho	CUSTOMER PERCIEVED VALUE-BASED PRICING	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.987**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	25	25
	CUSTOMER BRAND LOYALTY	Correlation Coefficient	.987**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above indicates a positive correlation coefficient of 0.987 between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. This means that an increase in customer perceived value-based pricing will lead to an increase in customer brand loyalty. The p-value of 0.000 suggests that customer perceived value-based pricing

and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state at 5% level of significance. This suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. We therefore concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study provide strong evidence of significant positive relationships between the three pricing strategies cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing, and customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty for the water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Each hypothesis tested through Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient indicates a high correlation coefficient and a p-value of 0.000, signifying the rejection of the null hypotheses and confirming that the pricing strategies have a significant impact on customer brand loyalty.

The study finds a significant positive relationship between cost-based pricing and customer brand loyalty, with a correlation coefficient of 0.975. This suggests that as the company's cost-based pricing strategy becomes more effective, customer brand loyalty increases. This aligns with the findings of Monroe and Krishnan (2015), who argue that cost-based pricing, when perceived as fair by customers, can enhance brand loyalty by ensuring customers feel they are getting value for money. The results are also consistent with Gauri et al. (2008), who found that transparent and consistent pricing strategies often foster customer trust and loyalty.

The significant positive relationship between competition-based pricing and customer brand loyalty, with a correlation coefficient of 0.972, indicates that customers are likely to remain loyal when the company's pricing is competitive within the market. This finding is in line with research by Kotler and Keller (2012), who suggest that competitive pricing can drive customer loyalty by positioning the brand favorably against competitors. The study also complements findings by Raju (2022), who found that competitive pricing strategies could lead to increased market share and customer retention in highly competitive markets.

The study shows the strongest positive relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty, with a correlation coefficient of 0.987. This suggests that when customers perceive they are receiving good value for the price they pay, their loyalty to the brand increases significantly. This finding supports the value-based pricing model advocated by Hinterhuber (2018), which emphasizes the importance of aligning price with the perceived value to drive customer loyalty. It also correlates with the research by Zeithaml (2018), who found that perceived value is a critical determinant of brand loyalty, especially in markets where customers have multiple choices.

Summary of Findings

The study sought to establish the relative impact of price strategies and consumer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. The summary is done in line with the research questions and objectives of the study based on the output of the descriptive and inferential statistical analyses guided to test the research hypothesis of the study. Thus, the major findings of this study are:

1. There is a positive significant relationship between Cost-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.
2. There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive-Based Pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.
3. There is a positive significant relationship between customer perceived value-based pricing and customer brand loyalty of water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated the significant influence of pricing strategies on customer brand loyalty within the context of the water bottling company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The research findings indicate that cost-based pricing, competition-based pricing, and customer perceived value-based pricing each have a strong positive correlation with customer brand loyalty, highlighting the importance of strategic pricing in maintaining and enhancing customer relationships. The rejection of the null hypotheses across all three pricing strategies underscores the critical role that well-structured pricing plays in customer retention and brand loyalty. Customers are more likely to remain loyal when they perceive pricing as fair, competitive, and aligned with the value they receive from the product. These insights are consistent with existing literature, reinforcing the notion that pricing is a vital

component of the marketing mix, particularly in competitive industries such as the bottled water market.

The study's results suggest that the water bottling company can significantly benefit from refining its pricing strategies by focusing on transparency, competitive positioning, and value communication. By continuously monitoring and adapting its pricing approaches to market conditions and customer feedback, the company can strengthen its market position and foster long-term customer loyalty. Ultimately, this research contributes to the understanding of how pricing strategies impact brand loyalty, providing actionable insights for the water bottling company and other businesses in similar markets. The recommendations derived from this study offer a roadmap for leveraging pricing as a tool to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty, which are essential for sustained business growth and success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study therefore recommends the following:

1. The company should maintain transparency in its cost-based pricing strategy. By clearly communicating how prices are determined, based on production costs and a fair margin, customers are more likely to perceive the pricing as just and reasonable, thereby enhancing their loyalty.
2. The company should continuously monitor competitors' pricing strategies to ensure that its prices remain competitive. This will prevent the loss of price-sensitive customers to competitors and help the company maintain its market share.
3. The company should clearly communicate the value that customers receive at the current price point, such as superior quality, health benefits, or environmental sustainability. Effective communication of these benefits can reinforce customers' perception of value and strengthen their loyalty.
4. Establish a feedback loop where customers can express their opinions on pricing and product value. This can provide insights into customer preferences and help the company adjust its pricing strategies to better align with customer expectations.

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